

1 **Composite indicator for the assessment of sustainability. The case of**
2 **Cuban nature-based tourism destinations.**

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14

15 **Abstract**

16

17 This paper presents a methodology for building a composite indicator to
18 evaluate the sustainability of nature-based tourism destinations. It combines
19 Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the distance to a reference point, and
20 Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) with the aim of addressing some of the
21 objections related to the aggregation procedure. The synthetic index obtained is
22 based on a representative series of sub-indicators of the concept of sustainable
23 tourist development as outlined by the World Tourism Organization (WTO). We
24 apply it to evaluate Cuban nature-based tourism destinations. The results
25 identify the strengths and weaknesses of destinations according to
26 sustainability, and serve as a guideline for tourism planning in the future.
27 Key words: Composite indicator, nature-based tourism, sustainability.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30

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31 In recent years, the concept of sustainability has received an immense amount
32 of attention in the socio-economic and managerial literature. This concept forms
33 a nexus between the development of society and the economic agents that
34 operate within it, and is bounded by the environmental, socio-cultural and
35 economic framework (Sancho et al., 2002). Its link with development began with
36 the publication of the report "Our Common Future" (Burtland Commission,
37 1987), which offered the most well-known definition of sustainable development.
38 This definition addresses the relationship between economics and ecology,
39 paying special attention to the social and cultural effects of economic growth
40 (Van Broeck, 2005).

41 The relationship between sustainability and tourism has been known since the
42 United Nations Earth Summit in June 1992, where efforts to apply the principles
43 of sustainability to tourism development began as an attempt to apply these
44 principles to the environment. From this time on, researchers and different
45 organizations have been working to achieve a commonly accepted definition of
46 sustainable tourism development. The World Tourism Organization (WTO)
47 defines it as the kind of tourism that "...makes optimal use of environmental
48 resources; respects the socio-cultural authenticity of host communities; ensures
49 viable, long-term economic operations, providing socio-economic benefits to all
50 stakeholders; requires the informed participation of all relevant stakeholders, as
51 well as strong political leadership; and also maintains a high level of tourist
52 satisfaction" (World Tourism Organization, 2004).

53 In addition to providing economic returns and a high-quality experience for
54 visitors, sustainable tourism development should therefore also aim at
55 protecting the natural environment and improving the quality of life of host
56 residents (Choi and Sirakaya, 2006; Larson and Herr, 2008). In fact, given
57 appropriate management and planning, this kind of tourism could be quite
58 beneficial for developing countries (Yildirim et al., 2008).

59 In line with this new paradigm, government policies for tourism planning are
60 directed toward a tourism model based on diversity, quality, and sustainability
61 that can improve the competitiveness of destinations.

62 Taking this into account, many countries need to diversify their tourist offer,
63 such as the Caribbean islands, where the main offer is based on sun and beach

64 tourism due to their similarities. Thus, Cuba, for example, should design and
65 implement policies aimed at diversification based on sustainability criteria.
66 The Tourism Ministry of the Cuban Republic (MINTUR) has prioritized nature-
67 based tourism, based on three main issues (Medina and Santamarina, 2004):
68 - Increasing concern for the environment at the world level. This is related
69 to the demand for tourist products associated with nature and the local
70 cultures, while respecting the environment.
71 - The potential in Cuba for developing this kind of tourism, either based on
72 the natural environment, or on the environmental wealth and cultural
73 diversity that exists in almost all regions of the country.
74 - The need to enrich the main tourist product of Cuba (sun and beach) with
75 the natural resources and cultural attractions of each region.

76 This process requires the use of tools to evaluate the destinations and define
77 the most suitable policies for their development. In this sense, indicators of
78 sustainable tourist development can be used to great effect.

79 In this study, the indicator system is understood as a set of measurements used
80 to provide data that would shed light on the links between sustainable tourism
81 and industry and on impacts on the natural and cultural environments. Each
82 component of the system evaluates an aspect of sustainability; these aspects
83 can be taken into account individually or in combination with the rest of the
84 system (Blancas et al., 2010a).

85 The indicator systems used in the planning process must be able to summarize
86 information in order to facilitate decision-making by the agents involved.

87 Composite indicators are widely used for this task and are defined as the
88 mathematical combination of individual indicators that represent different
89 dimensions of a concept whose description is the objective of the analysis (see
90 Saisana and Tarantola, 2002); their use represents an innovative approach to
91 evaluating sustainable development (Singh et al., 2009). They are invaluable
92 regarding their ability to simplify complex measurements (Singh et al., 2007),
93 such as sustainability, and are ideal for measuring multidimensional concepts
94 that cannot be captured by a simple sub-indicator (Saisana and Tarantola,
95 2002; Nardo et al., 2005a).

96 Many methods have been used to build composite indicators (OECD, 2008).
97 These methods depend more on the creator's abilities than the accepted rules
98 for building them. Thus, the analyst must choose which procedure to apply for
99 its construction according to the concept to be measured, such as choosing
100 which sub-indicators to use, how these are divided into classes, whether a
101 normalization method has to be used (and which one), the choice of the
102 weighting method, and how information is aggregated (Nardo et al., 2005b).
103 Given this background, the present work has two objectives: the first is to define
104 an indicator system to measure the sustainability of Cuban nature-based
105 tourism destinations; the second is to build a global composite indicator able to
106 measure the degree of sustainability of these destinations that gathers all the
107 information contained in the initial indicators, allowing us to make a comparative
108 analysis of these destinations.
109 Moreover, this indicator should allow a certain degree of freedom such that
110 each destination analyzed can be evaluated regarding its strengths and
111 weaknesses. Thus, we present a new two-stage methodology which combines
112 three techniques: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (statistical multivariate
113 technique), the distance to a reference point (multiobjective programming), and
114 Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) (linear programming technique). This has the
115 aim of obtaining a composite indicator which the end-user can understand,
116 making a comparative analysis, and identifying the sub-indicators and
117 dimensions that have the most influence on the global value.
118 Our study is divided into 5 sections. In the next section we describe how the
119 indicators were obtained to measure sustainability in the destinations. In section
120 3 we present the new aggregation procedure. The results and discussions are
121 presented in section 4 and the conclusions in the final section.

122

123 **2. Indicators to measure sustainability in Cuban nature-based tourism** 124 **destinations**

125

126 Cuba is considered to be one of the ten outstanding islands in relation to
127 biodiversity, which is mainly due to its tropical climate and the complexity of its
128 geological history and topography. It has six wetlands included in the Ramsar

129 List because of their international importance, one of which is the largest and
130 best conserved in the insular Caribbean: Ciénaga de Zapata. Cuba also has ten
131 National Parks. In total, 22% of the surface area lies within protected natural
132 areas. Despite these resources, the tourist offer has been fundamentally
133 oriented to sun and beach tourism.

134 However, although the number of visitors has changed little in recent years, in
135 2009, Cuba received 12.4% of the visitors to the Caribbean, 10% of whom went
136 to nature-based destinations, representing a remarkable increase compared to
137 the 0.26% recorded in 2004.

138 Even so, the Cuban tourist offer needs to diversify further and it should be
139 characterized by products that respect the sustainability of the tourist sector.
140 Thus, the construction of an indicator system to measure the sustainability of
141 the destinations is considered a necessity.

142 Several studies have attempted to determine the basic indicators to measure
143 the sustainability of tourism destinations (e.g. Farsari and Prastacos, 2001;
144 WTO, 2004; Gallego and Moniche, 2005; Díaz and Norman, 2006; Sancho et
145 al., 2007). Due to the absence of a group of unanimously accepted indicators,
146 as well as the different social, natural and economic conditions of the
147 destinations, the stakeholders select those indicators that better reflect the
148 needs and capacities of each region.

149 One example is provided by the Caribbean Zone of Sustainable Tourism
150 (CZST), which was established as a "...cultural, socioeconomic, and biologically
151 rich and diverse unit in which tourism development will depend on sustainability
152 (...), aimed at facilitating the integrated development of the Greater Caribbean."
153 (Association of Caribbean States, ACS, 2001). As a result, the "Proceedings
154 Manual for Sustainable Tourism Trainers" was created by Díaz and Norman
155 (2006) with the objective of monitoring the work aimed at creating more
156 sustainable tourism destinations in the Caribbean area.

157 In this work, the authors offer an indicator system for the development of a
158 global process that includes the Greater Caribbean and a local indicator system
159 adapted to the needs and capacities of the regions. The indicators were divided
160 into two groups:

161 - Normative indicators: common to all destinations and agreed in the
162 Convention for the establishment of the CZST.
163 - Local indicators: determined by the destinations (coastal, mountain, cities, etc)
164 based on their local priorities.
165 Given the lack of a unanimously accepted list of indicators (Maserà et al.,
166 2000), those chosen for a sustainability study should represent the needs of all
167 the agents involved in developing tourism in each destination.
168 There is continuing debate on the dimensions of sustainable tourism
169 development. These dimensions have been identified in different ways by
170 several authors (e.g., WTO, 2004; Van Broeck, 2005; Krajnc and Glavic, 2005;
171 Choi and Sirakaya, 2006; Díaz and Norman, 2006; Brun and Hirsh, 2008);
172 however, the currently accepted dimensions include all the sectors that operate
173 in any locality and their relationships in different contexts. In this study, we use
174 the three dimensions proposed by Díaz and Norman (2006) for sustainable
175 tourism development in the CZST:
176 Social dimension: related to people, their lives, the relationships they establish,
177 quality of life, employment, and other factors related to tourist development.
178 Economic dimension: related to tourism management and commercialization,
179 and material and financial resources.
180 Patrimonial dimension: related to everything concerning the natural and cultural
181 environment.

182

183 **2.1 Indicators**

184

185 The Workshop on Indicators of Sustainable Tourism, related to the
186 establishment of the CZST, took place on June 2008 in Viñales, Pinar del Río,
187 Cuba. The participants were stakeholders (public and private enterprises,
188 institutions, and groups or population sectors with a strong influence in the
189 region), executives from the Cuban Tourism Ministry, and other organizations
190 with information on the destinations.

191 In order to select the indicators for this study, we consulted the participants in
192 the workshop taking into account the indicators proposed by the WTO (2004),
193 Choi and Sirakaya (2006), Díaz and Norman (2006) and Sancho et al. (2007).

194 Each participant was given a list of indicators which they rated on a scale
195 ranging from 0 to 10, where 0 indicated that it was not necessary for the study
196 and 10 indicated that it was essential to the study. Any other value between 0
197 and 10 could be chosen.

198 Those indicators which were given a score higher than or equal to the median
199 of the scores were selected. In total, 39 indicators were selected (11 social, 14
200 economic and 14 patrimonial), which were representative of the concept of
201 sustainable tourism development proposed by the WTO (2004) (Appendix A,
202 Table A.1).

203 The social indicators included information related to improvements in living
204 conditions due to tourist activity, the social carrying capacity of the destinations,
205 changes in traditional occupations and social behaviour leading to
206 dissatisfaction among residents or visitors, the potential of tourism to generate
207 employment, perceived safety or risk in the destinations, and the quality of
208 public services.

209 The economic indicators included information on the level of tourist satisfaction,
210 seasonality of tourism, the tourist offer, infrastructure design and accessibility,
211 the economic benefits derived from tourism, and to what extent the territorial
212 plan for the municipality had been completed.

213 The patrimonial indicators included energy consumption, water consumption
214 and safety, the generation and disposal of residue, the cleanness of the
215 destination, intensity of use, and the impact of tourism at the environmental and
216 cultural level.

217

218 **2.2 Database**

219

220 Due to the Cuban interest in promoting nature-based tourism, all the sites with
221 the potential for developing this modality were analysed by an interdisciplinary
222 team composed of specialists from the Development Department of the Cuban
223 Ministry of Tourism, the Cuban Ministry of Science, Technology and the
224 Environment, the Institute of Planning, and the Ministry of Agriculture, with the
225 aim of developing an inventory of the environmental wealth of these
226 destinations.

227 As a result, a Working paper (MINTUR, 2003) was published that identified 64
228 sites covering 20100 Km² (18% of the Cuban surface area), 62 of which are
229 Protected Areas from different categories. These include seven Biosphere
230 Reserves, three areas that have been declared National Patrimony, one
231 Ramsar Site and one National Monument.

232 We consulted the list prepared by the nature-based tourism working group to
233 select the destinations for inclusion in our study. We chose those destinations
234 fulfilling the criteria proposed by Díaz and Norman (2006) considered necessary
235 for choosing a site as a sustainable tourism destination. These are:

- 236 ➤ A site proposed by tourism professionals.
- 237 ➤ A site visited by tourists.
- 238 ➤ A site with a local population.
- 239 ➤ A site that is locally organized and administered.

240 During the selection process, sites with accommodation for international tourism
241 were taken into account, such that data related to night stays and the
242 percentage of occupation could be collected. Thus, not all the sites listed were
243 included. Those without tourist accommodation or service installations were not
244 included because it was not possible to calculate some of the most important
245 indicators, such as the number of tourists, the occupancy ratio for official
246 accommodation, or average tourist stay.

247 It would have been useful to analyse the natural protected zones, but due to the
248 lack of information they could not be included. A new group of initial indicators
249 based on their characteristics would be needed for their inclusion.

250 In total, 15 nature-based tourism destinations were identified, three of which are
251 in the CZST: Viñales, Soroa and Ciénaga de Zapata.

252 These 15 zones are priority areas for the development of nature-based tourism
253 (MINTUR, 2003). They cover 7774, 97 Km² — approximately 40% of the total
254 surface area identified by the working group — and received 10% of the total
255 number of tourists who visited Cuba in 2009. Except for San Diego de los
256 Baños and Marea del Portillo, the other zones are located in or constitute areas
257 with some degree of protection according to the National System of Protected
258 Areas. There are three Biosphere Reserves: Soroa-Las Terrazas, Ciénaga de
259 Zapata, Baconao; five National Parks: Guanahacabibes, Viñales, Caguanes,

260 Desembarco del Granma, Alejandro de Humboldt; four Protected Natural
261 Landscapes: Hanabanilla, Guajimico–Gavilanes, Topes de Collantes, Mayarí;
262 and one Ecological Reserve: Alturas de Banao.
263 They are evenly distributed over the entire island: five in the East, five in the
264 center and five in the West.
265 To quantify the indicators, the destinations were assigned to the municipality
266 they belong to, because the municipalities have information systems for
267 evaluating social, economic and environmental conditions (Jam, 2007). In
268 addition, the organisation of the municipalities is less complex than that of the
269 provinces.
270 Of the 39 indicators selected, 23 are objective (obtained from sources of
271 statistical information), and the other 16 are subjective (reflecting the
272 perceptions of all agents involved in tourism development). Subjective
273 indicators were used because local populations are rarely included in
274 sustainability studies, even though they are important agents in the tourist
275 management process (Gursoy et al., 2002). Furthermore, objective indicators
276 are often stressed at the expense of the role played by subjective components
277 and perceptions in the satisfaction of internal clients (local population) and
278 external clients (tourists) (Sancho et al., 2007).
279 The objective indicators were based on information obtained in 2009 by the
280 Territorial Office of Statistics, which is part of the National Office of Statistics.
281 Data were also acquired from the Aqueducts and Sewer Systems Offices of
282 each municipality, the Union of Companies that recycle waste material, the
283 National Center of Protected Areas and the Vice-presidency of Monuments of
284 the National Council of Cultural Heritage.
285 Regarding the subjective indicators, both the tourists and the residents were
286 surveyed to obtain information on their perceptions of specific aspects relevant
287 to tourism development. Paper Assisted Personal Interviewing (PAPI) was
288 applied in both cases to analyze the qualitative variables using a five-point
289 Likert rating scale where, in the case of tourists, a rating of 1 indicates complete
290 disagreement and 5 indicates complete agreement. The investigation units
291 consisted of the international tourists lodging in hotels in all destinations;
292 systematic sampling with random start was used. In the case of residents, 1

293 indicates complete disagreement and 5 indicates complete agreement; a two-
294 stage cluster sampling procedure was performed. In the first stage, the clusters
295 were defined as the districts where the hotels are located and in the second
296 stage, the houses within the selected cluster were randomly chosen; the survey
297 was applied to all individuals between 17 and 70 years of age (for further
298 details, see Pérez 2011).

299 Thus, a quantified indicators system was obtained to compare nature-based
300 tourism destinations covering requirements such as relevance, accuracy,
301 timeliness and punctuality, accessibility and clarity, comparability and
302 coherence (OECD 2008) that guarantee the reliability of the synthetic indicators
303 derived from it.

304

305 **3. Aggregation procedure**

306

307 The construction of composite indicators involves stages in which subjective
308 judgments have to be made: the selection of indicators, how missing values are
309 dealt with, the choice of aggregation model, the indicator weights, etc. These
310 subjective choices can be used to manipulate the results (Nardo et al., 2005b).
311 As shown in different studies (e.g., Nardo et al., 2005a; OECD, 2008; Castellani
312 and Sala, 2009; Blancas et al., 2010a), there many ways to create a composite
313 indicator; other studies show that no methodology is more suitable than any
314 other for constructing synthetic indicators (Saisana and Tarantola, 2002; Nardo
315 et al., 2005a). When no information has been provided by the decision-makers
316 on the relative importance of the basic indicators, various procedures can be
317 used to determine the synthetic indicators where the weights are obtained using
318 different methods and all the weights are the same for all units. However,
319 although these methodologies provide homogeneity, they do not take into
320 account the special characteristics of each destination analyzed; this is the
321 reason we developed a method to determine a synthetic indicator that can be
322 easily interpreted and that takes these characteristics into account.

323 The methodology presented is divided into two stages. In the first stage, we
324 calculate a composite indicator for each dimension of the concept under
325 evaluation. In this case, we use a synthetic indicator called the distance-

326 principal component (DPC) developed by Blancas et al., (2010a). This indicator
 327 combines PCA with the concept of distance to a reference point based on a
 328 multicriteria decision-making philosophy. It is defined by the following formula:
 329

$$330 \quad DPC_i = \sum_{j=1}^q \left[VE_j \left(\sum_{k=1}^p IN_{ik} |Corr_{jk}| \right) \right]$$

331
 332 for $i=1,2,\dots,n$, where n is the number of observations, p is the number of
 333 original indicators, q is the number of components selected, VE_j is the variance
 334 explained by the j th component, and $Corr_{jk}$ is the correlation between the j th
 335 component and the k th indicator. IN_{ik} is the normalized value of the i th
 336 observation in the k th indicator, which is needed to normalize the data such that
 337 the measuring units used for each indicator have no effect on the final result.
 338 This procedure involves dividing the distance to the anti-ideal point by the
 339 difference between the maximum and the minimum value:

$$340 \quad IN_{ik} = \frac{I_{ik} - Min}{Max - Min}$$

341 where I_{ik} is the value of the i th observation in the k th indicator. We have chosen
 342 the minimum value of each indicator as the reference value, under the
 343 assumption that higher values indicate that the destination is more sustainable.
 344 Thus, when measuring the distance to the minimum value, we obtain the
 345 distance to an anti-ideal point; the greater the distance, the higher the
 346 destination's level of sustainability.

347 This approach makes the final result easier to interpret because the values of
 348 the initial indicators are defined according to their distance to a fixed reference
 349 value, such that the synthetic indicator is a linear combination of these
 350 distances and not of the principal components. The end-users' task is easier
 351 because they only have to choose the initial indicators and the criteria to select
 352 the components.

353 When the relative importance of the criteria is unknown, the weights are
 354 determined endogenously taking into account data variability.

355 The composite indicator is based on a reference point, which can be easily
 356 understood by the end-user. The method used to obtain it is transparent since

357 the principal components are the linear combinations of the distances between
358 the indicators and their reference units; thus, we evaluate the distance to the
359 anti-ideal point.

360 Once we have obtained the dimensional indicators, the second stage involves
361 calculating the global synthetic index. This involves evaluating each unit's
362 strengths. With this aim, we use Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), a linear
363 programming tool initially developed by Charnes et al., (1978) for evaluating the
364 performance of a set of peer entities that use one or more inputs to produce one
365 or more outputs. The method has been alternatively labelled the "Benefit-of-the-
366 Doubt" approach (Moesen and Cherchye, 1998; Nardo et al., 2005a; Cherchye
367 et al., 2007). This can be used to design composite indicators (see, for
368 example, Cherchye et al., (2006), Castellani and Sala, (2009)), among other
369 applications.

370 In this context, the synthetic index is defined for each unit as the ratio of the
371 weighted sum of its outputs and inputs, where the main aim is to determine the
372 weights that represent the highest efficient score for each unit, represented by
373 the following ratio: virtual output/virtual input. Virtual input and output values
374 provide information on the importance a unit attaches to particular inputs and
375 outputs to attain its maximum efficiency rating (Boussofiene et al., 1991). These
376 can be understood as normalized weights.

377 As pointed out by Murias et al. (2008), three features of DEA make it especially
378 appealing regarding constructing a composite indicator. First, benchmarking
379 provides a measure of performance based on real data. Best performance is
380 not a theoretical or abstract concept; it is defined by merely observing the best
381 performer. Second, DEA models possess the immense advantage of displaying
382 unit invariance, which makes the normalization stage redundant. Finally, by
383 allowing every unit to choose its individual weights, DEA respects the individual
384 characteristics of the units and their own particular value systems.

385 For the second stage, we use the dimensional indicators obtained for each
386 destination as initial information. They are positive and can be employed as
387 outputs to obtain the global synthetic index. We can use a single dummy input
388 with value unity for each destination; the global index value is the virtual output.
389 This model is formally equivalent to the original input-oriented, constant-returns-

390 to-scale DEA model presented by Charnes et al. (1978). In this way, the global
 391 synthetic index DEAPC (Data Envelopment Analysis after distance-Principal
 392 Component) for the i_0 observation is obtained by solving the following Linear
 393 Programming problem:

$$DEAPC_{i_0} = \underset{w}{Max} \sum_{j=1}^d w_j^{i_0} DPC_{i_0j}$$

subject to :

$$\sum_{j=1}^d w_j^{i_0} DPC_{ij} \leq 1 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n \quad (\text{normalization constraint})$$

$$w_j^{i_0} DPC_{ij} \geq \omega \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n; \forall j = 1, \dots, d \quad (\text{virtual output constraint})$$

$$w_j^{i_0} \geq 0 \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, d \quad (\text{non - negativity constraint})$$

394 where $w_j^{i_0}$ are the weights for the observation i_0 , DPC_{ij} represents the j th
 395 dimension indicator for the i th observation, d is the number of dimensions
 396 considered (in our case, three: social, economic, and patrimonial), and ω is a
 397 real number that represents the minimum value allowed for the j th virtual output
 398 for the i th observation.

399 The objective function chooses the weights that maximize the value of the
 400 composite index for observation i_0 . In the best situation, the global synthetic
 401 index takes a value of 1, which implies that the destination has a performance
 402 equal to its reference unit, and the synthetic index takes a value of 0
 403 representing the worst situation. Thus, the global synthetic index value takes
 404 the form $0 \leq DEAPC_i \leq 1$ for each destination, where higher values represent
 405 better overall relative sustainability.

406 As mentioned, synthetic indicators usually take into account the same weights
 407 for all the basic indicators such that all units are equally valued to avoid
 408 subjectivity. However, this may be less suitable in some cases as this approach
 409 does not permit emphasising any particularly positive or negative aspects of the
 410 units, which can be very helpful in decision-making. Thus, to allow the decision-
 411 makers to visualize this information we have to allow them to use different
 412 weights, but not to the extent that the results become biased.

413 To further restrict the endogenously selected weights, another constraint is
 414 added to the model: the virtual output constraint, that is, the establishment of a

415 lower bound ω for each virtual output. This guarantees that all the dimensions
416 included are taken into account.

417 Weights are dependent on the unit of measurement of the initial indicators; this
418 is the reason why the analysis is based on the virtual outputs. These are
419 particularly interesting because they do not depend on measurement units and
420 directly reveal how the respective outputs contribute to a composite indicator
421 value, thus showing their relative importance. Thus, this set of constraints
422 means that a certain amount ω of each dimension must be reflected in the
423 global indicator. This amount can be provided by the decision-maker or it could
424 be found by parametric analysis.

425 The proposed aggregation procedure thus offers a synthetic indicator in two
426 stages. In the initial dimensional stage, equal weights are used; in the second
427 stage, using DEA, different weights for each unit can be used, although only
428 when evaluating each dimension such that the special characteristics of the
429 units considered can be included. We note that combining DPC and DEA
430 methods only makes sense if there is no information on the weights of the basic
431 indicators. In other cases, if the weights are known, they can be used in the first
432 stage instead of those computed by PCA.

433 This procedure has the advantage of obtaining a composite indicator value
434 sensitive to the stakeholder's needs; more weight is given to those indicators for
435 which some destinations are in a better position compared to others included in
436 the study. In this way, the strengths and weaknesses of destinations can be
437 evaluated.

438 Weights are calculated such that the maximum possible value is determined for
439 the composite indicator in each destination. This indicates the flexibility of the
440 procedure, since the same level of importance does not need to be given to
441 each indicator in the different destinations. In addition, the use of DEA in the
442 second stage indicates how each dimension contributes to the overall value of
443 the DEAPC index.

444 Furthermore, a normalization procedure is not required in the second stage, a
445 composite indicator is not affected by the measurement units of the initial
446 indicators, and finally, the user does not need to select the indicators to build

447 the composite index again because the aggregation procedure is based on the
448 dimensional indicators obtained from the DPC index.

449

450 **4. Results and Discussion**

451

452 Before calculating the dimensional indicators, we need to determine the internal
453 consistency of the database. For this purpose we use Cronbach's Alpha
454 Coefficient (henceforth c-alpha) (Cronbach, 1951), because it assesses how
455 well a set of individual indicators measures a single uni-dimensional object
456 (OECD, 2008).

457 C-alpha is not a statistical test, but a coefficient of reliability based on the
458 correlation between individual indicators. High correlation indicates that
459 individual indicators are measuring the same underlying construct. Therefore a
460 high c-alpha, or high "reliability", indicates that individual indicators have
461 correctly measured the latent phenomenon.

462 In general, an acceptable value of c-alpha varies by discipline. Nunnally (1978)
463 suggests 0.7 as an acceptable reliability threshold. C-alpha was 0.7759 for the
464 indicators selected in our study and thus they are representative of
465 sustainability.

466 Once the internal consistency of the database was verified, we calculated the
467 composite indicators using the methodology described in Section 3. The results
468 are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

469

470 **4.1 Dimensional indicators**

471

472 The results of the first aggregation stage are shown in Table 1. In relation to the
473 social dimension, they show how the three best destinations are those where
474 social benefits have improved due to tourism, mainly those related to highways
475 and the transportation infrastructure. They are also the destinations least
476 negatively affected by tourism because of the low ratio of tourists to the local
477 population during the month of maximum affluence.

478 Regarding this dimension, the best destinations also report higher economic
479 benefits for the local community, due to the large number of local residents

480 employed in tourism; in the selected regions, 51% of total employees work in
481 tourism. The residents consider that the level of life has increased as a
482 consequence of tourism development.

483

484 **Table 1. Dimensional composite indicators.**

485

486 In the economic dimension, the best destinations have a good quality-price
487 relationship regarding food, have a high level of seasonality, a 50.2%
488 occupation rate of the official accommodation, and an average overnight stay of
489 4.7 above the mean for this tourist modality in Cuba.

490 These are the destinations in which the tourist offer is of the highest quality and
491 where the tourism industry offers the best performance. They attract the
492 greatest number of tourists — on average, 57327 tourists representing 54.58%
493 of the total number — and generate the highest tourism income — about 7.5
494 million dollars, representing approximately 51.4% of the overall income
495 generated in all the analyzed destinations.

496 In the patrimonial dimension, the best destinations have a higher percentage of
497 individuals with access to clean water (80.6%). They have the lowest intensity
498 of use, which is beneficial for the conservation of natural areas and the
499 patrimony, with an average of 23.8 tourists per Km², and a mean number of 3.5
500 tourists per day visiting monuments. From the residents' point of view, these are
501 the destinations where the tourists cause less destruction to the environment
502 and natural resources.

503 Table 1 also shows how some destinations, such as Bacanao or Habanilla, are
504 very balanced regarding the different dimensions, whereas others, such as
505 Topes de Collantes and Cuaguanes, are quite unbalanced, presenting
506 weaknesses and strengths that are more clearly revealed in the second stage of
507 the process.

508

509 **4.2 Global Composite Indicator**

510

511 After calculating the dimensional indicators, we calculate a global composite
512 indicator for each destination; this constitutes the second aggregation stage in

513 which we obtain the global composite indicator DEAPC by using the information
514 on the dimensional indicators obtained in the previous stage.

515 In addition, to control the contribution of each dimension to the global synthetic
516 index, we fix the value of ω to 0.15 such that each dimension is forced to
517 contribute at least this value to the global synthetic index. We note that the
518 different values of this parameter can be analysed to show the maximum value
519 that leads to unfeasibility due to the existence of one or more units that are
520 unable to contribute by this amount to the virtual outputs. In our case, $\omega=0.20$ is
521 unfeasible.

522 The values are shown in Table 2. The analysis is based on the virtual outputs,
523 which express information on the level of importance attributed to the
524 sustainability dimensions in each destination with the objective of obtaining the
525 maximum level of efficiency. This allows us to determine the influence each
526 dimension has in the global indicator value, and to identify the strengths and
527 weaknesses of the units under consideration.

528 The results show that there is no tie for first place. Thus, the most sustainable
529 site is Baconao, which has a virtual output greater than the level demanded for
530 the three dimensions; the patrimonial dimension is the strongest for this
531 destination.

532

533 **Table 2. Global Synthetic Index.**

534

535 Only two destinations had the lowest value allowed in some dimensions:
536 Guajimico, in the economic dimension, and Topes de Collantes, in the social
537 and patrimonial dimensions. These two sites occupied the lowest positions
538 according to the DPC indicator in these dimensions.

539 The proposed procedure for calculating the global indicator determines the
540 strengths and weaknesses for each destination using the virtual output values;
541 their sum is the value of the global index. Thus, destinations can be grouped
542 using the virtual output and they can be grouped according to the virtual output
543 with the highest score; this represents the dimension that has the best
544 performance in each destination (Fig. 1). Clusters can be obtained which allows
545 us to find common features between the destinations included in each group.

546

547 **Fig. 1. The distribution of the destinations according to virtual outputs.**

548

549 The social dimension is the most important in four destinations (27%), the
550 economic in two destinations (13%), and the patrimonial in nine destinations
551 (60%).

552 Similarly, destinations can be grouped according to the mean of the virtual
553 output for each group (Fig. 2).

554

555

556 **Fig. 2. Mean of the virtual output for clusters.**

557

558 In the first group of destinations, the social dimension was the most important
559 followed by the patrimonial and then the economic. In the second group, the
560 economic dimension was the most important, followed by the patrimonial, and
561 then the social. In the third group, the patrimonial dimension was the most
562 important, followed by the economic, and then the social.

563 Compared to other methodologies, the PCA method cannot be used under the
564 assumption of unknown weights for the basic indicators without losing
565 information; this is due to the relationship between the number of units analyzed
566 and the number of basic indicators. Thus, we chose the synthetic index GPSI
567 (Blancas et al., 2010b), using the weights computed by our method in the first
568 stage.

569

570 **Table 3. Comparison between DEAPC and the GPSI Global Synthetic**
571 **Index.**

572

573 The results of using the GPSI method are similar in some units (see Table 3).
574 However, under this method, cities such as Ciénaga de Zapata are in the first
575 position due to the effect of a single basic indicator, i.e., its geographical
576 extension, which is much greater than the other cities. Traditional methods do
577 not limit the effect of a single basic indicator. On the other hand, our DEAPC
578 method is able to limit this kind of effect on a single dimension, in which case

579 this unit takes fifth place in the ranking. This results in a more balanced and
580 reliable ranking, not only regarding extreme values in the basic indicators, but
581 also regarding the values of the weights.

582

583

584 **5. Conclusions**

585

586 The present study presents a methodology for determining an indicator system
587 that represents the concept of sustainable tourist development as outlined by
588 the WTO in order to measure the sustainability of Cuban nature-based tourism
589 destinations. In contrast to other studies, we also quantified them according to
590 the available statistical information, calculated the internal consistency of the
591 system to measure the underlying phenomenon, and constructed a composite
592 indicator for each destination to represent its degree of sustainability.

593 The proposed methodology aggregates all the information contained in the
594 initial indicators and represents a new tool that can contribute to the decision-
595 making process in nature-based tourism destinations.

596 The aggregation procedure has some advantages compared to other current
597 procedures. First, it is divided into two stages, such that the dimensions
598 included in the sustainability concept can be analysed (first stage), and then a
599 global composite indicator for each destination is calculated (second stage).

600 In the first aggregation stage, the composite indicator DPC is calculated and the
601 weights of the indicators included in the process are endogenously determined
602 such that each initial indicator is weighted by the amount of information
603 assigned to the synthetic measure. The information is completely transparent to
604 the end-user, who can identify in each dimension the characteristics that have a
605 stronger or weaker influence on the degree of sustainability obtained.

606 Moreover, the dimensional composite indicators are easily understood by the
607 end-user, because they are based on the distance to a reference point, and the
608 calculation method is transparent. The principal components are the linear
609 combinations of the distances between the indicators and their reference units;
610 thus, when the composite indicators have higher values the situation is more

611 sustainable. This makes the results of the Principal Component Analysis more
612 understandable thus facilitating the creation of the composite indicators.
613 In this way, the use of DEA in the second stage allows all the available
614 information to be included, because it considers the dimensional indicators as
615 initial information; therefore, a new indicator selection procedure is not required
616 to build the global composite indicator. In addition, the weights are
617 endogenously determined and a normalization process is not needed; thus,
618 fewer decisions are required during the aggregation process.
619 The proposed methodology allows all the dimensions to be included in the
620 composite indicator and separates the synthetic value into parts that represent
621 the contribution of each dimension to the global value. Thus, it makes it easier
622 to obtain a detailed analysis, the dimensions that constitute a destination's
623 strengths and weaknesses can be identified, and managers can focus on
624 solving the main problems.
625 The two-stage synthetic indicator proposed combines statistical methods, which
626 are more objective, with efficiency methods. This offers the possibility of
627 considering the strengths of the destinations analyzed as well as providing the
628 decision-makers with useful information by which they can improve these
629 destinations.
630 Finally, we would like to point out that this methodology may be applied to other
631 destinations by making simple changes to the original database, and can also
632 be used to analyze other issues in different areas.

633

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641

642

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738

739 **Appendix A.**

740

741 **Table A.1. Indicators system to measure the sustainability of Cuban**
742 **nature-based tourism destinations.**

743

Table 1. Dimensional composite indicators.

Cuban Nature Destinations	Dimensional Indicators DPC					
	Social	Ranking	Economic	Ranking	Patrimonial	Ranking
N.P. Guanahacabibes	0.5048	10	0.4522	4	0.6667	4
N.P. Viñales	0.4904	11	0.3955	10	0.5106	14
San Diego de los Baños	0.4464	13	0.3576	14	0.6349	8
Soroa-Las Terrazas	0.5189	8	0.4062	7	0.5840	13
Ciénaga de Zapata	0.5571	4	0.4369	5	0.6417	7
Hanabanilla	0.5221	7	0.4006	8	0.6319	9
Guajimico	0.4169	14	0.3151	15	0.6011	11
Topes de Collantes	0.4111	15	0.5350	2	0.4416	15
Alturas de Banao	0.5310	6	0.3832	12	0.5935	12
N.P. Caguanes	0.5699	2	0.3913	11	0.6309	10
Mayarí	0.5640	3	0.3980	9	0.6788	2
N.P. Desembarco del Granma	0.5111	9	0.3815	13	0.6748	3
Marea del Portillo	0.4483	12	0.4356	6	0.6496	5
Baconao	0.6264	1	0.5430	1	0.7120	1
N.P. Alejandro de Humboldt	0.5474	5	0.5115	3	0.6446	6

Table 2. Global Synthetic Index.

Cuban Nature Destinations	Global Synthetic Index DEAPC				
	Ranking	DEAPC	Social Virtual Output	Economic Virtual Output	Patrimonial Virtual Output
N.P. Guanahacabibes	4	0.8798	0.1842	0.2152	0.4803
N.P. Viñales	14	0.7529	0.3912	0.1883	0.1734
San Diego de los Baños	13	0.7906	0.1629	0.1702	0.4575
Soroa-Las Terrazas	12	0.8056	0.4139	0.1934	0.1983
Ciénaga de Zapata	5	0.8735	0.2033	0.2080	0.4623
Hanabanilla	9	0.8365	0.1905	0.1907	0.4553
Guajimico	15	0.7352	0.1521	0.15	0.4331
Topes de Collantes	10	0.8218	0.15	0.5218	0.15
Alturas de Banao	11	0.8075	0.4236	0.1824	0.2016
N.P. Caguanes	6	0.8551	0.4546	0.1862	0.2143
Mayarí	3	0.8843	0.2058	0.1894	0.4891
N.P. Desembarco del Granma	7	0.8542	0.1865	0.1816	0.4862
Marea del Portillo	8	0.8390	0.1636	0.2074	0.4680
Baconao	1	1	0.2286	0.2585	0.5130
N.P. Alejandro de Humboldt	2	0.9176	0.1998	0.4989	0.2189

Table 3. Comparison between DEAPC and the GPSI Global Synthetic Index.

Cuban Nature Destinations	Global Synthetic Index DEAPC		Global Synthetic Index GPSI	
	Ranking	DEAPC	Ranking	GPSI
N.P. Guanahacabibes	4	0.8798	5	0.04
N.P. Viñales	14	0.7529	14	-0.5
San Diego de los Baños	13	0.7906	11	-0.21
Soroa-Las Terrazas	12	0.8056	10	-0.19
Ciénaga de Zapata	5	0.8735	1	1.18
Hanabanilla	9	0.8365	7	-0.13
Guajimico	15	0.7352	15	-0.54
Topes de Collantes	10	0.8218	13	-0.44
Alturas de Banao	11	0.8075	8	-0.14
N.P. Caguanes	6	0.8551	9	-0.15
Mayarí	3	0.8843	4	0.1
N.P. Desembarco del Granma	7	0.8542	6	-0.12
Marea del Portillo	8	0.8390	12	-0.27
Baconao	1	1	2	1.08
N.P. Alejandro de Humboldt	2	0.9176	3	0.27

Table A.1. Indicator system for measuring the sustainability of Cuban nature-based tourism destinations.

Nº	Indicator	Dimension	Sign
IS ₁	Perception by the local population that an improvement in highways and transportation infrastructure is because of tourism.	Social	Positive
IS ₂	Perception by the local population that an improvement in public services is because of tourism.	Social	Positive
IS ₃	Proportion of tourists to the local population (during the month of maximum affluence).	Social	Negative
IS ₄	Perception by the local population that tourists have an undesirable effect on lifestyle at the destination.	Social	Negative
IS ₅	Perception by the local population that tourism contributes to preventing young people from leaving the municipality.	Social	Positive
IS ₆	Number of local employees in tourism.	Social	Positive
IS ₇	Percentage of women employed in the tourist sector.	Social	Positive
IS ₈	Percentage of the local population working in the tourist sector.	Social	Positive
IS ₉	Perception by the local population that the quality of life has increased because of tourism.	Social	Positive
IS ₁₀	Tourist evaluation of safety at the destination.	Social	Positive
IS ₁₁	Tourists' perceptions of the quality of public services (illumination, transport, bank services, etc).	Social	Positive
IE ₁₂	Perceptions regarding quality-price ratio of lodging at the destination (private and non-private).	Economic	Positive
IE ₁₃	Perception of quality-price ratio of restaurants at the destination.	Economic	Positive
IE ₁₄	Evaluation of the quality of tourism workers (in hotels, restaurants, and tourist information points).	Economic	Positive
IE ₁₅	Occupancy ratio of official accommodation.	Economic	Positive
IE ₁₆	Proportion of tourists in the months of maximum and minimum affluence.	Economic	Negative
IE ₁₇	Average tourist stay.	Economic	Positive
IE ₁₈	Percentage of seasonal employees in tourism.	Economic	Negative
IE ₁₉	Tourist offer.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₀	Tourist evaluation of accessibility and attractiveness.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₁	Number of tourists.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₂	Tourist spending.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₃	Destination profitability.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₄	Average tourist-day expenditure.	Economic	Positive
IE ₂₅	Percentage of general economic plan completed according to desired aim.	Economic	Positive
IP ₂₆	Energy consumption by tourist per day.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₂₇	Energy consumption of renewable sources per year attributable to tourism.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₂₈	Volume of daily water consumed by tourists.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₂₉	Percentage of local population with access to clean water.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₀	Volume of solid waste attributable to tourism.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₃₁	Reduction of solid waste attributable to tourism.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₂	Tourist evaluation of cleanliness at the destination.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₃	Size of the area dedicated to tourism.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₄	Number of tourists per square kilometer.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₃₅	Intensity of use of cultural sites.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₃₆	Tourist evaluation of activities related to natural resources at the destination.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₇	Perceptions by the local population concerning environmental damage caused by tourism.	Patrimonial	Negative
IP ₃₈	Perceptions by the local population concerning the stimulation of local crafts and culture due to tourism.	Patrimonial	Positive
IP ₃₉	Tourist evaluation of the conservation of natural resources and heritage at the destination.	Patrimonial	Positive

Fig. 1. The distribution of the destinations according to virtual outputs.

Fig. 2. Mean of the virtual output for clusters.

